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AXBOROT XAVFSIZLIGI

ANALYSIS OF THREATS TO INFORMATION SECURITY OF PROTOCOLS AND LIGHTING CONTROL SYSTEMS

(PhD), docent Khudoykulov Z.T.

Tashkent University of Information Technologies

zarif.khudoyqulov@gmail.com

Seidullaev M.K.

Tashkent University of Information Technologies

mr.madiyar95@gmail.com

Abstract- The article discusses possible threats in the field of information security when using PLC technologies (power line communications). Such technical solutions enable control and feedback with controlled devices, but these technologies do not meet the required level of information security. The article suggests ways to solve this problem.

Keywords- information security, information security threat, information system, lighting control, PLC technologies.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most modern trends in the field of energy saving and energy efficiency is the introduction of intelligent control systems. The most effective solution is considered to be the use of PLC technologies (power line communications), or the control of energy-consuming terminal devices over power networks. The technical solutions used in practice make it possible not only to control energy flows, but also to implement "feedback" in order to control the operational parameters of the controlled system. According to a similar scheme, the so-called. "internet of things". There are even data transmission solutions for a limited range of consumers in the "last mile" conditions. There are a large number of offers of control controllers and modems on the market for connecting information channels to power supply networks. At the same time, most technical solutions use proprietary technologies and do not take into account information security aspects at all. This work is devoted to the study of this

problem.

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of the presented work is to develop recommendations for the construction of lighting control systems in terms of information security. To achieve it, the following tasks were solved:

- analyzed the basic requirements for the safe operation of industrial programmable controllers;
- studied the main security threats in automated control systems for process equipment;
- Identified current security threats;
- measures have been developed to minimize the risks associated with the operation of lighting control systems.

Common threats in the field of information security in automatic control systems based on the FSTEC threat bank are:

- the threat of unauthorized remote out-of-band access to hardware;
- the threat of inconsistency in the rules for access to big data;
- threat of substitution of a wireless client or access point;
- the threat of interception of control by an automated process control system;
- the threat of interception of information entered and output to peripheral devices;
- threat of privileged flow interception;
- the threat of intercepting the exception of a signal from a privileged block of functions;
- threat of interception of one-time passwords in real time.

There is a huge amount of scientific material concerning the technical aspects of using these technologies, for example, the order of connecting controllers or modems [1–3]. In this case, the main attention is paid to the issues of electromagnetic compatibility and transfer characteristics of communication channels using power lines [4–6]. A limited number of studies is devoted to the study of technical channels of information leakage in PLC systems [7–9].

Based on the material studied, it can be concluded that the lighting control system is multi-component. With this approach, the number of actual threats associated with the interception of control of the object increases significantly. On the basis of the Institute of Electronics and Lighting Engineering, Moscow State University N. P. Ogaryov also considered the security issues of information

systems designed to control technological equipment and built on the principle of the “Internet of Things [10].

In this regard, it seems necessary to investigate the reliability of control protocols for lighting systems. Based on the analysis of proposals for solving the issues of remote control of lighting systems, we state that the most common protocols for controlling lighting systems are industrial protocols 1-10B, DMX, Dali. The first of the noted protocols is analog, and its use is limited to small lighting installations, mainly for domestic lighting.

DMX and Dali protocols make it possible to control lighting installations, where control objects can be located at a distance from control systems at a distance of several hundred meters to several kilometers. At the same time, the Dali protocol is open and is supported by such large manufacturers of lighting fixtures as OSRAM. It should be noted that these protocols, as specified in the specification, are not protocols for secure data transfer and require the use of additional means of ensuring information security.

When updating threats in lighting control systems, it was taken into account that the main element that ensures the functioning of the lighting control system is a telecommunications network. Through this network, information is collected from various types of sensors and transferred to the main controller for processing. The controller, after processing the information, transmits control signals to the actuating elements. Through the central controller, the lighting system is configured and controlled by the legal user, and also through it, if necessary, the specified information is transmitted to the user of the system via an external network when he is not in the room (for example, about unauthorized entry). Such a telecommunications network can be built using both wired and wireless communication channels, such as WiFi, Bluetooth or 3G.

Results and discussion

To build a general threat model for the lighting control system, a general information model was built motion system (Figure 1).

When constructing this general threat model, special attention was paid to the PLC level, since for the information system under study this level is the most vulnerable in terms of protocol reliability and, in addition, violation of security properties at this level leads to the most significant disruptions in the operation of the managed system.

Figure 1. The general model of the information system

IV.CONCLUSION

Based on the presented analysis, we draw the following conclusions.

1. For all known security threats, there is a significant probability of their implementation.

2. To compensate for the risks associated with the implementation of the presented threats, it is necessary to use additional measures and technical solutions.

3. When designing lighting control systems, it is necessary to additionally be guided by standards in the field of information security.

The minimum scope of measures to ensure the safe operation of lighting systems must comply with the requirements of the regulator¹⁰ and contain the following sets of measures:

- identification and authentication of access subjects and access objects;
- access control of access subjects to access objects;
- limitation of the software environment;
- protection of machine data carriers;
- registration of security events;
- anti-virus protection;

- intrusion detection;
- control (analysis) of information security;
- ensuring integrity;
- ensuring accessibility;
- protection of technical means.

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